

Labour Migration and Remittance Inflow in Nepal: Trend and Policy Analysis

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Abstract — This paper examines the impact of labour migration and remittance inflow in Nepal. The major objective is to analyze the trend and pattern of the labor migration and the volume of remittance inflow in Nepal. However, the specific objectives are to review and examine the government policies regarding foreign employment and remittance in Nepal and to recommend the appropriate policy measures for the promotion of foreign labor migration and remittance inflow in Nepal. This study is primarily based on secondary data and it is also based on previously published literatures. The foreign labor migration and remittance inflow in Nepal is increasing trend. This study shows that the remittance has become the major mainstay of economy contributing about 25% in the National GDP.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, foreign employment has played a critical role in the Nepali society. Its nature, scope and dimension have undergone fundamental changes since the first known foreign employment in the beginning of the eighteenth century during the process of national unification when an exodus of peasants left to work in the tea estates in Darjeeling and Assam of India. In the early nineteenth century, hundreds and thousands of Nepali hill people joined the British Army and fought on the side of the Allied powers both during the World War I and World War II. The beginning of the construction boom in the emerging economies in East Asia and the Gulf in the 1980s provided yet another opportunity for young Nepalis to venture out for foreign employment in pursuit of a descent and dignified life. Foreign employment gives them employment and income opportunities which are not possible in the country. It has led to political and economic empowerment of people, including women, offering alternative to land-based wealth (Sharma & Gurung, 2009).

Remittance holds great significance in Nepal where one-fourth of the population lives below the poverty line. According to World Bank, Nepal is among the top five countries in the world with remitted income amounting to 23 per cent of the national GDP. Statistics show that remittances bring in one hundred billion rupees each year to Nepal. In 2010, Nepal received \$3,507 million (The World Bank, p. 15 cited in Singh, 2011). According to World Bank, remittance has definitely reduced headcount poverty rate in the country. It has been stimulating much needed economic development.

Increased globalization has resulted in expanding employment opportunities in newly industrializing countries like Malaysia, Taiwan, and South Korea and also in the Gulf, to which the workers from Nepal (and other South Asian Countries) have migrated in significant numbers over the last decade or so. Even in developed countries like Japan, the UK, Europe and the USA new opportunities for migration have opened up, even though immigration controls and

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other restrictions ensure that much of this migrant labor is unofficial if not illegal. But the attraction of cheap and unorganized foreign labor has created a growing demand, to which there has emerged an equally lively response and supply. (Dahal, 2004)

Increased in the demand for oil has created the new jobs in the oil exporting countries and decrease in the population growth rate in the developed countries made a shortage of human resources in these countries to keep their economic growth. These developments made the demand for the skilled and semi skilled labors from the developing countries to these countries. Many millions of people are now living and working in another country far away from their countries of birth. There is a flow of millions of people from South to North and flow of billions of dollars from North to South. These people regularly remit a substantial proportion of their earnings to their families. The financial flows generated by these migrants by way of remittances are very substantial. (World Bank, 2006).

The wave of globalization and liberalization has induced the Nepali youths for better living standard, which is the important pull factor for the international migration. Beyond this, high population growth, unemployment, food scarcity, political instability are also the strong pull factors (Singh, 2006).

Currently due to the wide spread conflict in the country many workers view foreign employment as their only viable option. After the origin of the Maoist insurgency it has not only broken the employment opportunities but also has distorted peace and social order. In such a miserable situation, remittance has become only source to sustain the economy of Nepal (NRB, 2006).

Migration of an individual is influenced by various factors. It has both the positive as well as the negative impact on both the origin and the destination of the migrant.

The number of Nepalese going for the foreign employment is increasing every year. Apart from

Malaysia and Korea, the number of those going to the Gulf countries for employment has been particularly high. During the FY 2006/07 the total number of persons issued permit for foreign employment through institutions means reached 773,592. A total of 204,533 were added in FY 2006/07 and 152,682 up to mid-March were added. Thus, the total number of persons issuing permit for foreign employment reached 30,807. (Economic Survey, MoF, 2007/08)

The current major issue of the migration is remittance. The remittance has played vital role in the economic prosperity of the recipient countries. Remittance usually has two dimensions: it contributes to the foreign exchange reserve of the country and it raises the total economic activities through the particular individual. From the beginning of the contribution of the remittance in the nation's foreign exchange has not been negligible. Moreover, it has the role to compensate the import of our country since trade deficit in our regular character. On the other hand, the identity of the 'Lahures' in the area of Nepal has become as walking by being decorated, energetic, healthy and smart, wearing neat and clean clothes, house with dazzling made of tin or stone. (Dahal, 1999).

Migration of people from one place to another is a usual phenomenon since the beginning of human civilization. The migration in the beginning was for the sake of food and exploring new places for security purpose. But gradually the migration has taken the shape in diverse form and now has become very essential and common in each and every part of the world. International labour migration is one of the integral components while talking about international migration. Millions of people are moving around the world (especially from the developed world) are leaving their usual place of residence for seeking better employment opportunities and supply food for their dependents. Globalization and integration of regional economics have added impetus to the growing mobility of workers across borders (ILO, 2003 cited in Bhattarai, 2006)

Poverty and the inability to earn enough or produce enough to support oneself or a family are major reasons behind the movement of work seekers from one place to another. These are not only characteristics of migration from poor to rich states; poverty also fuels movement from one developing country to others where work prospects seem-at a distance, at least-to be better (OHCHR, 2004 cited in Bhattarai, 2005).

Labour migration has, in the 21st century, moved to the top of the policy agendas of many countries - countries of origin, transit and destination. Most of the world's estimated 150 million migrants are people searching for improved economic opportunities abroad.

By observing the trend of labour migrants it seems that most of them are either unskilled or semi skilled and a few portion of them are highly skilled. According to estimates by non-government group, there are over 19 million Asian migrant workers in Asia and over 25 million Asian migrant workers working across the world. At least half of the migrant workers are women, and many are in domestic work, the entertainment industry and also in irregular works (Marwan Macan-Marka, IPS, 2003 cited in Bhattarai, 2005). A huge number of Nepalese workers go abroad to work in the absence of fruitful local employment opportunities. Migration is nothing new to Nepal, and the total stock of Nepalese nationals working overseas (excluding about one mission in India) in different capacities is estimated to be about half a million (ILO-DFID 2002). The history of formal entrance of Nepalese citizens in foreign employment begins in 1814-1815 after the Nepal-British India war. A total of 4,650 Nepalese youngsters were recruited to the British armed forces as a British-Gurkha regiment.

So far in the Nepalese context, foreign labour occupation has been developed as an emerging business in Nepal. But the business has not remained as a dignified profession at all. The reports about irregularities in foreign labour migration, problems

faced by potential labour migrants before and after their departure for foreign employment are not properly addressed from the policy level.

Statistics show that the remittance sent by the migrant workers is nearly one hundred billion each year and the amount of remittance has kept great importance to the national economy. Some economists have analysed Nepalese economy as remittance economy, which has played a prominent role to keep the national in balance in the difficult financial situation of the country. The amount of remittances sent through the informal channel are not calculated yet but that is to be estimated as equal to it come from the formal channel (Bhattarai, 2005)

While observing the government policies and programmes, it is found several lacking to protect the rights of the migrant workers and assure their safe migration in the country of destination. Government has made promotional policy regarding foreign employment but at the same time less attention has been paid to provide services and facilities in the home ground. Some of the provisions mentioned in the Foreign Employment Act-2042 are like controlling the foreign employment business rather than promotional one (Ibid).

Despite the great extent, international labour migration has long been paid little attention in Nepal. On the one hand the importance of international labour migration as an income source for Nepal's households and to the economy of Nepal as a whole remained officially invisible. This is due to the fact that the officially registered international labour migrants only represents a small proportion of the real number, and the value of remittances is not fully recorded in the national accounts. On the other hands, until the late 1990s, most studies of Nepal emphasised the importance of agriculture in the national economy, and the National Planning Commission (NPC) deemed agriculture to be the key to the rural development (NIDS: 2004). But the scenario of economy is changed i.e. agricultural based economy turned toward remittance based economy which has been proved by several studies

conducted by governmental and non governmental agencies. Thus, it is needed to address the issue of international labour migration from the policy level, which could assist to promote safe migration and the management of labour migration in an effective way. This study has explored some of the policy oriented issues that should be improved and amended in the future (Ibid).

Foreign employment has proved as an alternative source of employment for the Nepalese. According to the data provided by the Department of Labor and Employment Promotion, 205,033 people had gone for the foreign employment in the FY 2006/07. While during the first eight months of the FY 2007/08, 152,652 people went for the foreign employment. The inflow of remittance also mounted to Rs 82.42 billion during the first eight months of the FY 2007/08 from Rs 1.14 billion over the same time period of the previous year giving rise by 28.1 percentages. During the first three months of the FY 2008/09, according to the Central Bank, the inflow of remittance shot up by 80.7 percentages. The big jump in the remittance has also helped to boost the country's overall Balance of Payment (BoP). According to the quarterly report of NRB, Nepal's BoP recovered from a deficit of Rs 5.6 billion in the first quarter of FY 2007/08 to a surplus of Rs 7.7 billion in the first three months of FY 2008/09. Similarly the remittance also has the significant contribution of 18 percentages on the National GDP.

Remittance has thus become one of the largest sources of the external finance for Nepal. But, the trends and patterns of the foreign employment, volume of the remittance inflow, government policies regarding the foreign labor migration has not been fully examined using the recent data and information.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dalen, Groenwold and Fokkema, (2005) concluded that only the altruism and the self interest are not the absolute motives for the migration. They further concluded that the family rise and the net earning potential of the migrants have stronger effects on

the flow of the remittance than the net earning potential of the households in the country of origin. Regarding the highest remittance recipient countries globally in 2003 were the countries of the East Asia and the Pacific, Latin America and the Caribbean and the South Asian respectively.

CEDA (1975) conducted two different studies in four districts of western Terai (Banke, Bardia, Kailali, and Kanchanpur). Objectives of the study conducted in Banke and Bardiya was to study migration in the resettlement area. The findings of the study in the remaining two districts were the identification of one way migration from Terai and age, sex and occupation selective of the migrants. The study suggested the need of government investment in roads and irrigation on the hills to lower migration in Terai. Kansal (1982) in his research, 'Migration, Remittance and Rural Development' reviewed preceding research of migration with reference to the remittance. He found the origin of Nepalese emigration to be at the Anglo Nepali war in 1814 and was totally for the recruitment purpose. The Indian authority was not only open to them but also managed for their permanent settlement. However, the then Nepal government had discouraged it. The Prime Minister Bir Shamsar JBR, for the first time relaxed the policy and encouraged the people to join the British recruitment. So, 20,000 Nepalese male joined British regiment even during First World War.

Pant, (2005), stated that remittance is one of the least volatile sources of foreign exchange earnings for the developing countries. According to her that other kinds of capital flows tend to rise during the period of economic booms and fall during the recession. In the case of remittance, when a country's economic crisis prevails then the people of that country migrated to the foreign country seeking employment that ultimately causes to rise the foreign currency earnings. She concludes that remittance is important to the receiving countries at the micro and macro level. Migrant activities are a drain on the labor and the capital resources of the migrant sending areas characterized as the 'Dual

Disease'. Remittance receiving households tends to be better off than that not receiving ones.

Karki (2006) in his desertion 'Foreign Employment and Remittance Economy Of Nepal; A case study of Dhuseni VDC, Illam district' attempted to identify the impact of foreign employment and remittance of Nepal, socio-economic characters of foreign employees, sources of financing and cost for foreign employment, change brought by foreign employment and remittance in the household economy and uses of remittance. His study is based on both the primary and the secondary data. Primary data were collected from the sample houses in the study area and secondary data were collected from the publications of CBS, NPC, WB etc. for the purpose of the comparison of the composition of foreign employment and remittance in his study. He has analyzed the data by using simple statistical tools like percentage and ratio.

The research report of NRB (2006) conducted by the special study section of NRB entitled as 'Foreign Employment, Remittance Economy And Nepal' states that the migration of Nepalese workers started after 1816's peace treaty between Nepal and Britain. Most of the people of that time are migrated to work in the British regiments. The study examines about the historical perspectives, present condition. The trend and dimension of remittance, the problems associated with the remittance and its measurements, the use of of the gained money as well as the skills, the investment pattern of that remittance and also the employment condition of the people returned from the foreign employment. It also examines about the Nepalese foreign employment system and its objectives with other questions related with the remittance. This study concludes that apart from India, about 86% of the people migrated to Gulf countries like Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Dubai etc. Rest percent are migrated to the other countries of the world. This study concludes that even though the role of manpower companies in obtaining work permit, government acceptance letter, tickets etc. is very helpful but most of the manpower agencies

of Nepal are looking the people in the name of foreign employment.

RESEARCH METHODS

This report is primarily based on secondary data available with Ministry of Labour and Transport Management (MoLTM), Ministry of Finance (MoF), Department of Foreign Employment (DoFE), International Organization for Migration (IOM), Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS), Nepal Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) and Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB). It is also based on previously published literatures and secondary information. A lot of data have been used to explain and justify the concepts. Qualitative as well as quantitative data have supported the argument. There are various sources of data and information that vary in nature. Different forces and factors have been used to link the main concept explained in the paper. However, only information from government sources is used for explanation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amount of remittance Nepal receives every year has been increasing. The figure below shows the amount of remittance received each year.

Figure 1

Sources: World Bank (2011)

According to MPI Data Hub "Migration facts, stats and maps," remittance received increased to \$3507 million in 2010 from \$111 million in 2000. Nepal received remittances worth \$200,

\$740, \$771, \$823, \$1212, \$1453, \$1734, \$2727 and \$3000 million in 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008 and 2009 respectively (The World Bank, p. 15 cited in Singh, 2011).

This shows the number of Nepali labor hired by foreign countries has gone up significantly. Population growth rate of Nepal stands at 1.6 per cent in 2011 whereas remittance growth rate exceeded 17 per cent during the same period (IFAD, p. 10). Around 55 per cent of the country's total population falls under the economically active (working population) group aged between 15 to 59 years. According to Nepal Demographic and Health Survey, twenty-seven per cent of the working population has left the country.

Therefore the number of Nepali labor working abroad has been increasing through the years. The following figure shows the number of Nepali migrant abroad according to Department of Foreign Employment.

Table 1:

Year	No. of Nepali Migrants
1994	3605
1995	2159
1996	2134
1997	3259
1998	7745
1999	27796
2000	35543
2001	55025
2002	104739
2003	105055
2004	106375
2007	204433
2008	449051
2009	219965
2010	294094
2011	354543
2012	530250

Source: Government of Nepal (2013)

The number of Nepali labor migrant increased to 530,250 in 2012 from 3,605 in 1994. In the years 1995, 1996, 1997, 1998, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004 the number of Nepali migrant was 2,159, 2,134, 3,259, 7,745, 27,796, 35,543, 55,025, 104,739, 105,055 and 106,375 respectively. Similarly in the year 2007, 2008, 2009 and 2011 the number of Nepali migrant laborers increased to 204,433, 249,051, 219,965 and 354,543 respectively. On an average, at least 1,000 migrant workers fly out of the country every day. Foreign employment continues to be a major demand among young Nepalese looking for income and job opportunities.

Although Nepal has officially opened 108 countries in terms of labor employment, Malaysia and Gulf countries alone account for 90 per cent of Nepali migrant workers. The table below shows the destination of Nepali male and female migrant workers as of 2010.

There are no sources in the current document

Country	No. of Male Migrants	No. of Female Migrants	Total
Afganistan	472	0	472
Algeria	35	0	35
Bahrain	16554	119	16673
Hong Kong	86	32	118
Israel	65	0	65
Japan	16	6	22
Jorden	249	0	249
Kuwait	3916	0	3916
Lebanon	756	867	1,623
Libya	1,185	0	1,185
Macau	39	0	39
Malaysia	145,942	996	146,938
Maldives	45	0	45
Mauritius	33	0	33
Oman	1,276	2	1,278
Pakistan	145	0	145
Poland	27	31	58
Qatar	26,964	29	26,993

Russia	8	0	8
Saudi Arabia	46,040	7	46,047
Seychelles	28	0	28
UAE	20,936	410	21,346
USA	22	0	22
South Korea	2,118	0	2,118

During the period 2006 to 2011, 361,464 Nepalese had gone to Malaysia, 351,544 to Qatar, 246,448 to Saudi Arabia, 178,535 to United Arab Emirates and 20,303 to Bahrain. Malaysia and Gulf countries of Saudi Arabia, Qatar, United Arab Emirates and Bahrain are major destinations for Nepali migrant workers. As shown in the table above, Malaysia is believed to be a popular destination with a total of 361,464 documented Nepali migrant workers. A total of 146,938 Nepali migrant workers left for Malaysia in 2010 (Bhattarai, 2005 pp. 49-52).

We see a huge number of Nepali labor entering foreign markets every year. No wonder, the remittance we receive comprises 23 per cent of the total GDP. Despite the growth in remittance, productivity has not increased as is evidenced by the fact that the living standard of the people in Nepal has not markedly improved. Though urban areas do seem to show some improvement, the same cannot be said of rural areas where even the basic amenities of life are far beyond the reach of the populace.

Another important aspect that has to be considered is the undocumented labor migration. Security is another concern. Reports about irregularities in foreign labor migration and problems faced by migrant workers before and after their departure for foreign employment are not addressed at the policy level. The Department of Foreign Employment has already recorded 1,898 outsourcing frauds worth Rs. 1.04 billion in the first eleven months of the last fiscal year. About 152 cases amounting to Rs. 403.31 million reached the court. In the last one year, outsourcing fraud cases have increased by 46.68 per cent (Bhattarai, 2005 p. 49).

Contribution to GDP

The share of remittance in the GDP cannot be ignored. Currently Nepal is among the top five countries in the world with remittance amounting to 23 per cent of the national GDP. Tajikistan, Tonga, Lesotho and Moldova rank above Nepal. It is estimated that the percentage share of remittance in the GDP will rise to 25 per cent in the years to come. The share of remittance in the GDP in percentage (Nepal Rastra bank) is given below:

Year	Share of Remittance to GDP(%)
2001-2002	10.3
2002-2003	11
2003-2004	10.9
2004-2005	11.1
2005-2006	14.9
2006-2007	13.8
2007-2008	17.4
2009-2010	19.6

Source: Quarterly Economic Bulletin, NRB 2011

National GDP stood at Rs.1219 billion in 2010. Although around one-fifth of the national GDP is contributed by remittance, one-fourth of the population lives below the poverty line. This shows that rise in remittance did nothing or very little to uplift the impoverished population.

Figure 1. Trend Line Showing Remittance growth rate and real GDP growth rate

Though remittance growth rate accelerated since 2000, Nepal's real GDP growth rate registered only a gradual increment.

Analysis of Existing Government Policies Regarding Foreign Employment in Nepal

Nepalese Foreign Employment Act-2042

The foreign Employment Act-2042 is the act no 26 of the year 2042 and the date of Royal Seal and Publication are on 2042/7/14/4. This is act made to provide for the matters relating to foreign employment, which was first amended on 2049 B.S. The basic features of this act can be summarized as follows;

- It deals about license process of employment agency and foreign employment enterprises
- Provision of prior permission to be taken by the license holder employment agency
- Provision of giving public information to the potential migrant workers through the advertisement
- Compulsory involvement of government representatives during the selection process of the workers
- Justifiable contract mechanism between the recruitment agency and the worker
- Counseling: The recruitment agency should provide information on the subject of the country to be visited by the worker. The information includes geographical location, culture, labour laws as well as economic, political and social conditions of the concerned country
- Complain Mechanism is also provisioned for the benefit of the worker: If the employment agency has not fulfilled its contract responsibility or licence-holder who has not taken necessary and appropriate action to make the contract conditioned fulfilled

- Compensation- The license holder employment agency has to provide compensation to the worker in case they do not find contracted job or any explosion or injuries occurred by the worker

Current act on foreign employment act senses a control oriented. The preamble of the Employment Act-2042 has specified that the act is behind this act of to regulate and manage the employment from the government level. This came in practice in 1985 and foreign employment was quite new working area of the government. At that time, manpower agencies were not experienced and private sector institutions were not capable to work on foreign employment.

National Labour Policy 1999

National Labour Policy (NLP) 1999 (2058) dealt the government policies and programs on different labour issues where the issue regarding the promotion and reliability of international labour migration is also highlighted to a great extent. The provision mentioned in the NLP regarding issues of international labour migration is a complementary action to increase the effectiveness of Foreign Employment Act-2042.

While observing the document, the last part of the objective section of the policy is dealt about the recruitment service profession. The provision states "by providing continuity to foreign employment service profession, special attempts shall be made for its institutional development"

Similarly, in the policy section of NLP, under "Employment Promotion, Trainings and Human Resource Development" has mentioned a provision regarding foreign employment stating that "to increase foreign employment and to make reliability of the current foreign employment, appropriate changes and amendment on previous Foreign Employment Act and Policy to encourage foreign employment company shall be adopted"

The working policy section of NLP four major policies regarding migrant workers is incorporated. The policies are

- For the protection of rights and security of Nepalese workers in foreign country, diplomatic mission of Nepal, to the countries where the greater possibility of foreign employment exists and other government agencies shall be mobilized and in addition labour attaché shall be kept according to necessity
- For the expansion of foreign employment and increment of the reliability of its business, a high level advisory committee shall be constituted with the participation of Ministry of Labour, Home, Finances and National Planning Commission and foreign employment entrepreneurs' organizations
- For the development of foreign employment, if necessary, foreign employment institution shall be established, with the participation also of the private sector and
- To encourage the skilled human resources to the self employment or foreign employment, the programme to expansion the self-employment and foreign employment shall be preceded as campaign by providing loans at the concession rate without security.

Recommending Appropriate Policy regarding Foreign Employment and Remittance

Even though the labor policies address the reductions of the leakages of the remittance inflow through the informal sectors, there is the requirement of the transparent and complementing rule with the reduction in the transfer cost that can encourage the workers for the formal transfers.

There should be the execution of the current budgetary provision of accessing concessional credit to the migrant workers. They also need some fiscal and technical assistance to run small- scale business enterprises from their small savings.

The government should offer a fund and help the returnees for institutional investment, so that the investment can be diverted from the daily consumptions and the real estate.

Women send more remittance than the men. As such for the future economic safety and the recognition of the women contributions, there should be a special provision for the women labor migrants in the plans and policies.

For the safe and formal labor migration, bilateral and multilateral agreements should be made with coherent policies. Diplomatic mission and the monitoring agencies should be increased. Moreover, labor attaché should be established on all the nations associated with the Nepalese labor migration.

New and effective institution should be established in order to promote the foreign labor employment so that exact and reliable data can be attained and problem of contradiction regarding the number of foreign employers in the respective countries can be easily known and estimated.

The government should help in increasing the capacity of potential migrants by providing trainings, educations, and orientation according to the need of the labor importing countries.

There should be Institutionalizing of an effective law of enforcement mechanism and providing access to the justice. The role of the administration should be made clear so that cheated people can get justice.

CONCLUSION

The foreign labor migration and remittance inflow in Nepal is in an increasing trend. This study shows that the number of Nepali labor migrant increased to 530,250 in 2012 from 3,605 in 1994. This shows that on an average, at least 1,009 Nepali migrant workers fly out of the country every day. Similarly, According to MPI Data Hub "Migration facts, stats and maps," remittance received increased to \$3507 million in 2010 from \$111 million in 2000..

The foreign employment Act 2007 has made several provisions regarding the rights and the securities of the foreign labor. Moreover, it has also encouraged the private sectors for the transfer of remittance into the country through the formal channels.

The labor Acts and policies are being amended according to the requirements. They seem to be important only as the written documents for the future reference, but are not implemented strictly and effectively by the government. The diversion of the remittance inflow in the productive sector, the entire security of the labor migrants, governments support to the foreign employers has not been realized according to the plan. The remittance as such has become only the basis of debt reducing factor rather than investment in the productive sectors.

Even though the labor policies address the reductions of the leakages of the remittance inflow through the informal sectors, there is the requirement of the transparent and complementing rule with the reduction in the transfer cost that can encourage the workers for the formal transfers.

For the safe and formal labor migration, bilateral and multilateral agreements should be made with coherent policies. Diplomatic mission and the monitoring agencies should be increased. Moreover, labor attaché should be established on all the nations associated with the Nepalese labor migration.

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